

Autoencoder-Based Dynamic Coded Modulation for 6G NOMA Uplink

Adriano Pastore, Carles Antón-Haro, P Aswathylakshmi, Pablo Fernández-Rodríguez
Information and Signal Processing for Intelligent Communications
Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC)
Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, 08860 Castelldefels, Spain
E-Mail: {adriano.pastore,carles.anton,aswathylakshmi,pallathadka,pablo.fernandez}@cttc.cat

Abstract—We showcase a NOMA uplink implemented with software-defined radios that demonstrates dynamic link adaptation using an end-to-end learned, coded modulation system. A model-free approach to training using over-the-air samples helps illustrate the superiority of neural implementations of mappers and demappers that can factor in the myriad hardware impairments encountered in practical communication systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) is a wireless communication technique that allows multiple devices to communicate simultaneously in the same frequency band, thereby allowing for an efficient spectrum use to meet the demands of increased connectivity and data rates for 6G. However, this requires a careful design of the transmitted messages that get superimposed in the power domain, as well as signal cancellation algorithms at the receiver, to recover the message from each device. Traditional NOMA systems that use standard constellations (QAM, PAM, PSK) to modulate signals rely on transmit power disparities to distinguish different user signals. This under-utilizes the signal space and results in suboptimal performance. Machine learning (ML) offers promising techniques to intelligently design signal mappers for NOMA, jointly optimizing modulation and coding to efficiently utilize the signal space, leading to gains in error performance, data rate, and spectrum utilization.

Empirical evidence in several contexts has shown the benefits of data-driven methods to outperform traditional, model-driven PHY layer designs. In particular, the concept of end-to-end (E2E) learning of the PHY layer of wireless communication systems, has attracted considerable attention.

On the hardware side, high-performance software-defined radio modules have become increasingly affordable, so that a 5G/6G air interface can be simulated in realistic conditions and offer a playground for experimental validation of proposed 6G PHY layer solutions. In this context, we aim to make an over-the-air demonstration and offer a graphical visualization of

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PHY layer schemes that are end-to-end learned. Specifically, we focus on the joint design of coding and modulation, which is one area where important improvements over state-of-the-art, separation-based, quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) schemes, have been recently demonstrated.

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II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a two-user multiple-access uplink with two single-antenna transmitters and one single-antenna receiver, whose system equation in baseband representation, on any single carrier, is given by

$$\mathbf{y} = h_1 \mathbf{x}_1 + h_2 \mathbf{x}_2 + \mathbf{w} \quad (1)$$

with complex inputs $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathbb{C}^n$, complex channel gains $h_1, h_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ and AWGN $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^n$. The transmitters and receiver are equipped with FEC and interleaving functions as depicted in the block diagram from Figure 1 on the next page. The processing blocks subject to implementation with neural networks vs. a conventional approach, are shaded in blue. This NOMA baseband uplink model serves as the basic setup.

III. FEATURES

Our autoencoder-based neural mappers and demappers can perform geometric shaping for uplink NOMA to find the optimal combination and mapping of the constellations for the two transmitting users. They are trained using a model-free approach with over-the-air samples obtained from software defined radios which allows them to adapt to common hardware impairments. Our demo will have the following features:

- Automated link adaptation to adjust to different modulation sizes and code rates.
- Dynamic switching of the SIC order between the users depending on their relative signal strengths.
- Live tracking of the BER/BLER performance of our neural mapper-based NOMA scheme compared against conventional coded modulation baselines.
- Real-time visualization of scatterplots of received baseband signal(s) and constellation(s).

Fig. 1: Flowgraph of the two-user NOMA uplink

IV. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE

Our setup is composed of the following inventory:

- 2 Ettus Research USRPs X310 and 3 daughterboards.
- 1 GPU-equipped laptop for controlling the USRPs and for displaying the learned constellations and performance curves in realtime.
- 3 omnidirectional antennas: 2 transmitters and 1 receiver.

On the software side, we rely mainly on the Matlab 5G toolbox and Python scripts. We also resort to NVIDIA's open-source Python framework Sionna for rapid prototyping.

V. KEY INNOVATIONS

We have already shown simpler versions of this demonstrator at earlier events: A point-to-point variant of this demo was shown at the Mobile World Congress 2023 (Figure 2) directed at a general audience, where it has proven highly successful in catching the interest of visitors at our booth. A simpler version with SIC was exhibited at the EuCNC 2022 conference and ICMLCN 2024. Some key innovations with respect to these earlier versions are the following:

- We implement automated adaptation of the modulation and coding scheme with rate adaptation, as well as automated selection of the decoding order.
- Error-correcting codes (5G NR LDPC codes) are included, unlike our earlier demos.
- While earlier demos leveraged a coding gain from custom multidimensional constellations learned by a neural network, here we focus on a more practical approach of designing the mappers/demappers with neural nets. The observed gain, with respect to a state-of-the-art baseline, will be related primarily to the geometric shaping performed by the neural coded modulation, rather than to a coding gain.
- A variant of the demo consists in showing over-the-air computation with deep geometric shaping.

Figure 3 shows the scatterplots of the neural mapped constellations for the two users in NOMA uplink. The constellations shrink/expand into the signal space with varying signal strengths and interference levels between the users.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Our work showcases the superior block error rate performance of the neural coded modulation schemes compared

Fig. 2: Neural NOMA Uplink demo at MWC 2023

Fig. 3: Scatterplots of the learned constellations for the two users in NOMA uplink.

to conventional modulation schemes in a realistic 5G/6G orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) NOMA uplink setup with two users. This demonstrates the advantages of using neural mappers/demappers which can adjust the modulation and coding rates of the users based on their relative signal strengths to optimize the sum rate at the receiver. Training using over-the-air samples makes the neural coded system more robust to practical impairments. We also illustrate how E2E trained schemes attempt to discriminate between both user signals by occupying distinct regions of the signalling space, thus solving a special case of a sumset sphere packing problem. We provide graphic visualizations displaying scatterplots of the learned constellations in real time.